

D7.7

Update Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

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Abstract	<p>This deliverable provides the final update to the CRAFT-OA Exploitation and Sustainability Plan, summarising how the project's results have been embedded into long-term operational and governance frameworks. It consolidates progress made since D7.2 and presents measures securing the continuity of services, tools and resources developed under</p>

CRAFT-OA. The report outlines how technical components and community processes have been anchored within existing infrastructures and institutional partners, including OpenAIRE and PKP, and aligned with the emerging EDCH (OPERAS). It also describes how sustainability has evolved from a planning phase into an implemented structure, reducing reliance on project-based funding cycles and strengthening collective stewardship across organisations. As a result, CRAFT-OA concludes with a portfolio of interoperable, community-driven services that extend beyond the project's lifetime and form a durable foundation for the continued development of the European Diamond OA publishing ecosystem.

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Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
AMU	Université d'Aix Marseille
BCP	Best Current Practices
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DISCO	Discoverability Companion
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
FHH/ SUBHH	Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg/Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Hamburg
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
ICM	The Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling
IPSPs	Institutional Publishing and/or Service Providers
IPTPs	Institutional Publishing Tool & Technology Providers

JMEF	Journal Metadata Exchange Format
KER	Key Exploitable Result
LH	Living Handbook
LMS	Learning Management System
MU	Masarykova Univerzita
NCC	National Capacity Centre
OE	OpenEdition
OA	Open Access
OJS	Open Journal Systems
OMP	Open Monograph Press
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
OPERAS	Open Access in the European Area through Scholarly Communication
OPS	Open Preprint Systems
PKP	Public Knowledge Project
SeDOA	Service Centre for Diamond Open Access (Servicestelle für Diamond Open Access)
SRCE	University of Zagreb University Computing Centre
TIB	Technische Informationsbibliothek

TSV	Federation of Finnish Learned Societies
TTF	Tools and Technology Task Force
UGOE	Georg-August-Universität Göttingen
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Table of Content

1	Executive Summary	9
2	Introduction.....	10
3	Results and exploitation	12
3.1	Overview of key project results	12
3.2	How results are being used	14
3.3	Key integrations supporting exploitation	16
4	Sustainability framework	17
4.1	Principles and process underlying the sustainability framework	17
4.2	Diversity of results and sustainability pathways	17
5	Sustainability arrangements for individual KERs.....	19
	KER 1 – Diamond Discovery Hub	20
	KER 2 – OJS Core Feature Enhancements.....	21
	KER 3 – OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard	22
	KER 4 – Publisher’s Living Handbook.....	23
	KER 5 – OJS Diamond Plugins	24
	KER 6 – Guide to Scholarly Indexes	25
6	Dependencies, risks and continuity measures	27
7	Conclusions	32
8	References	33
8.1	List of References	33
8.2	List of Websites.....	33

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, “D7.7 Update of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan”, provides the final account of how CRAFT-OA’s results have been consolidated, embedded and transitioned into long-term operational settings. It updates and complements D7.2¹, moving from initial strategies and planning frameworks to implemented sustainability models backed by institutional commitments.

The report covers six validated Key Exploitable Results (KERs):

- the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH),
- OJS Core Feature Enhancements,
- the OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard,
- the Publisher’s Living Handbook for Diamond OA (Living Handbook),
- the OJS Diamond Plugins, and
- the Guide to Scholarly Indexes.

Together, these results form a coherent portfolio covering the technical, organisational and knowledge layers of Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing. The portfolio as a whole is anchored across institutional partners, established infrastructures such as Public Knowledge Project (PKP), Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), Open Access in the European Area through Scholarly Communication (OPERAS) or Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE), which together provide overarching coordination and ensure operational continuity across services beyond the project’s lifetime.

The sustainability framework has been implemented and validated across five dimensions: 1) ownership, 2) hosting, 3) technical support, 4) editorial and content updates, and 5) community and user management. This update confirms that responsibilities have transitioned from project-based roles to commitments from institutional structures, supported by stable hosting environments and active user communities. It also documents how individual results interconnect through functional and knowledge-based links. The DDH provides validated Diamond OA journal data that feeds into the OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard for analytics and monitoring. The Open Journal Systems (OJS) Diamond Plugins ensure interoperability between publishing platforms and discovery or indexing services, while the Guide to Scholarly Indexes and the Living Handbook complement these technical components with shared documentation, standards and training resources. Together, these links create a federated, yet coherent, service environment that supports continuous data flow, learning, and reuse across the Diamond OA ecosystem.

CRAFT-OA’s exploitation and sustainability work demonstrates how technical development, institutional governance and community participation can jointly sustain the Diamond OA model. The project’s contribution is structural: it delivers a distributed, interoperable and community-driven framework that reduces reliance on project-based funding cycles while strengthening shared stewardship among infrastructures.

¹ D7.2 Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (Draft), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12697575>

2 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable provides a final overview (M36) of how the CRAFT-OA project has supported the long-term sustainability and practical use of its key results. It describes what has been achieved, how the main project outputs have been embedded into existing infrastructures and communities, and which measures ensure that these results remain active and maintained after the end of the project.

It follows and updates D7.2 (Exploitation and Sustainability Plan, M18), which presented the initial sustainability framework and preliminary strategies for each Key Exploitable Result (KER)². CRAFT-OA applied a framework based on a KER-driven model: each result has a responsible organisation, a named champion, and a defined pathway for continuity. During the project, exploitation was coordinated through KER champions, who acted as operational leads and short-term owners to guide development and integration. D7.7 demonstrates continuity with these earlier plans, showing how initial models have been implemented, tested and consolidated. The added value of this update lies in providing sustainability arrangements, confirmed ownership commitments and evidence of integration with external infrastructures and communities.

The work has been carried out within WP7 dedicated to technology exploitation and sustainability, with the overall goal of ensuring the uptake of CRAFT-OA outcomes within the European Diamond Open Access (OA) ecosystem. In this way, the report fulfils the commitments defined in the Grant Agreement regarding the long-term use of results, sustainability planning and collaboration with partners.

The analysis presented in this report draws on the full body of documentation produced throughout the project. It builds on the ongoing coordination within WP7 and close collaboration with the KER champions, supported by shared materials and records maintained in Confluence³ and other internal repositories, as well as publicly accessible outputs such as the CRAFT-OA project website, Zenodo community and dissemination records documenting conferences, webinars and publications. It also reflects the discussions and feedback gathered during the sustainability sessions at the CRAFT-OA final conference in October 2025, complemented by insights from earlier meetings, monitoring activities, results collections including KER and other project outputs, datasets, standards and event documentation. Taken together, these materials provide a comprehensive picture of how exploitation and sustainability were developed within CRAFT-OA.

The structure of this report is as follows:

- Section 2 summarises the key project results and their exploitation pathways.
- Section 3 introduces the sustainability framework and the underlying principles that guided planning across results.

² Project KERs are the primary outcomes identified for their high potential to benefit stakeholders. KERs include both tangible and intangible outputs, such as software improvements, databases and policy recommendations.

³ Confluence is an information management system provided by Atlassian, which offers a number of functionalities supporting collection of information, management of project activities such as deliverables and milestones, action assignment as well as templates that can be used to harmonise content. More details here: <https://www.atlassian.com/software/confluence>.

- Section 4 presents the sustainability arrangements for each KER, outlining ownership, hosting, maintenance, and community aspects.
- Section 5 consolidates key dependencies, risks and continuity measures that underpin the long-term sustainability of the results beyond the project's lifetime.
- Section 6 concludes the report with an overall reflection on sustainability achievements and the continuation of collaboration within the Diamond OA ecosystem.

3 RESULTS AND EXPLOITATION

3.1 Overview of key project results

Since D7.2, the list and scope of KERs in CRAFT-OA have been revised and finalised. The project initially defined five KERs; during the second reporting period, another one was added (KER6) and the titles of several were refined to reflect their actual form and use. The final list of six KERs is presented below:

KER1 – Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH)

Registry of Diamond OA journals in Europe. Provides verified, structured information on Diamond OA journals, ensuring their visibility, discoverability and recognition.

KER2 – OJS Core Feature Enhancements

Set of core improvements to Open Journal Systems (OJS) addressing multilingual metadata, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance, and data export standards to align OJS with European interoperability and accessibility requirements.

KER3 – OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard

Analytics and monitoring service within OpenAIRE MONITOR offering Diamond OA publishers a consolidated view of publishing activity, visibility, funding links and impact indicators.

KER4 – Publisher’s Living Handbook for Diamond OA (Living Handbook, or LH)

Dynamic documentation platform referencing results from CRAFT-OA on technical, organisational, and policy knowledge from institutional publishing practices, enabling reuse and adaptation by Diamond OA communities.

KER5 – OJS Diamond Plugins

Collection of interoperability plugins that connect OJS with aggregators and registries, improving visibility, metadata exchange, technical compliance, and efficiency of Diamond OA journals, thus supporting editors in their daily effort.

KER6 – Guide to Scholarly Indexes

Knowledge base and catalogue describing major scholarly indexes, their inclusion criteria, and metadata requirements, helping Diamond OA publishers improve journal visibility and indexing readiness.

Together, six KERs represent the validated results of CRAFT-OA. They contribute to the technical chain of Diamond OA publishing and are integrated into partner infrastructures such as Public Knowledge Project (PKP), Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), Open Access in the European Area through Scholarly Communication (OPERAS) or Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE), and ensure continuity and institutional anchoring beyond the project lifetime. Each KER has a defined owner, hosting environment and long-term responsibility, further detailed in Section 4.

In addition to the KERs, CRAFT-OA produced a set of complementary outputs documented in the internal Confluence workspace and mirrored on the internal EU results platform.

Standards. CRAFT-OA contributed to the development of shared specifications for metadata interoperability in the Diamond OA ecosystem. The main outcome here is the Journal Metadata Exchange Format (JMEF), an Extensible Markup Language-(XML-)based standard created within the scope of the DDH and currently used by the OJS JMEF plugin. It enables structured metadata exchange between journals, aggregators and registries, and is recorded as the principal standardisation result of the project.

Datasets. Several open datasets were produced to document and support project activities. They include the Knowledge Base of Scholarly Indexes⁴, which underpins the Guide to Scholarly Indexes, and the Dataset: Results of the CRAFT-OA requirement survey for OJS installation and update toolkit⁵.

Other results. These include open documentation, interviews, evaluations and training materials, including those developed for the Technical Standards Toolkit⁶, alongside the six criteria for identifying Diamond OA journals and their verification guidelines. The project also consolidated technical patterns around federated Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), including a reusable framework for single sign-on access and trust-and-identity best practices aligned with European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) AAI developments. These results capture practical lessons from implementation and collaboration with the Diamond OA community. They represent the applied knowledge produced across work packages and form the basis for reuse and uptake.

Taken together, these outputs extend the scope of the six KERs by supporting standards, datasets and materials developed during implementation. They consolidate the technical and practical foundations of the project and provide traceable evidence of how CRAFT-OA outputs were structured, tested and prepared for continued use beyond the project lifetime.

In addition to these results, CRAFT-OA maintained a continuous stream of communication and dissemination work⁷. Although reported separately, this effort is closely connected to the overall results framework. The materials presented at conferences, shared through webinars and summer schools, and published in Zenodo and other repositories reflect the same body of work documented in the project's KERs and other results. In this way, these activities act as an extension of the results framework, ensuring that outputs developed within CRAFT-OA are contextualised and made visible to their target communities. The final overview and documentation of this work are provided in D7.6.

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/17103786>

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/10853503>

⁶ <https://service.tib.eu/toern/course/view.php?id=36>

⁷ D7.6. Second update for communication and dissemination, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17531163>

3.2 How results are being used

This section describes how CRAFT-OA results have been put into practical use in the Diamond OA network. It covers both the operational deployment of project outputs and their reuse across related initiatives and communities.

The exploitation approach in CRAFT-OA evolved from the ongoing operational work of the consortium rather than from abstract design planning. Partners worked on the basis of their existing service portfolios and communities, which defined where new developments were needed and for whom. As a result, exploitation was not a separate layer added afterwards but an inherent part of project development. Some outputs also emerged in response to concrete implementation needs identified along the way, reflecting the same practice-driven logic. This grounded approach made it possible to align new tools and documentation with the real workflows of infrastructures and service providers, creating a coherent basis for long-term continuity.

The table below provides an overview of how each KER has been implemented and integrated into existing infrastructures. It highlights KER ownership, collaboration and current operational use.

KER	Champion	Collaboration	Operational use
KER1 Diamond Discovery Hub	Hanna Varachkina (UGOE)	DOAJ, ICM, OPERAS, EDCH	The Hub operates as part of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH). Technical maintenance is provided by The Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM); editorial curation by Georg-August-Universität Göttingen (UGOE). The product owner role has transitioned from UGOE to DOAJ.
KER2 OJS Core Feature Enhancements	Antti-Jussi Nygård (TSV)	PKP	Improvements of OJS address multilingual metadata, GDPR compliance, and data export standards that have been developed with PKP to ensure inclusion in the OJS core ⁸ and maintenance through PKP community channels.
KER3 OpenAIRE Publisher	Leonidas Pispiringas (OpenAIRE)	SRCE	The Dashboard runs within OpenAIRE MONITOR and provides analytics for Diamond OA journals.

⁸ These functionalities have been included in the core of OJS 3.5, the current LTS version.

Dashboard			It is hosted and maintained by OpenAIRE, with University of Zagreb University Computing Centre (SRCE) as a pilot partner, and is used for monitoring and reporting activities.
KER4 Publisher's Living Handbook for Diamond OA	Isabella Meinecke (FHH/SUB HH)	EDCH, FHH/ SUBHH, UGOE	The Living Handbook brings together the results developed within CRAFT-OA and makes them available as a dynamic documentation and training resource for technical staff, journal editors and institutional publishers. The Moodle-based platform is maintained by Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg/Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Hamburg (FHH/SUBHH). FHH/SUBHH is also responsible for the knowledge base in Service Centre for Diamond Open Access (SeDOA). There is potential for synergies.
KER5 OJS Diamond Plugins	Martina Dvořáková, (MU)	MU, AMU, TIB	The OJS Diamond Plugins provide interoperability features for OJS-based publishing platforms, supporting metadata exchange, visibility, and data validation. The plugins are released on GitHub.
KER6 Guide to Scholarly Indexes	Arnaud Gingold, (OpenEditio n)	EDCH (Tools & Tech TF)	The Guide to Scholarly Indexes provides an overview of major scholarly indexes and their inclusion criteria. It offers structured information on indexing policies and metadata requirements to help Diamond OA publishers assess and improve journal visibility. The Guide is publicly available on Zenodo and GitHub.

Table 1.

Beyond the six KERs, several complementary results developed within CRAFT-OA are also in active use. The JMEF is applied in the DDH and OJS Diamond Plugins to support structured metadata exchange. Training materials and sessions from the Technical Standards Toolkit remain publicly available and support stakeholders in

implementing technical publishing standards. The dataset from the CRAFT-OA requirement survey for the OJS installation and update toolkit and the Knowledge Base of Scholarly Indexes are public and continue to serve as reference data for technical upgrades and indexing alignment.

Overall, exploitation in CRAFT-OA operates on two levels – through the continued operation and partnerships with hosting infrastructures, and through the public availability and reuse of supporting outputs across the Diamond OA community.

3.3 Key integrations supporting exploitation

Exploitation in CRAFT-OA has been strongly shaped by technical and organisational integrations, which connect project results with the broader Diamond OA ecosystem. These integrations ensure that outputs developed within the project do not remain standalone tools but become part of shared operational environments.

Several infrastructures have played a decisive role in embedding CRAFT-OA results. PKP in its role as the release management organisation for the developer community provides the framework for the inclusion of OJS Core Enhancements and interoperability plugins into the global OJS release process, enabling long-term uptake by the journal community. The core enhancements will also be available in Open Monograph Press (OMP) and Open Preprint Systems (OPS). OpenAIRE hosts and operates the Publisher Dashboard, providing a direct link between Diamond OA journals and research monitoring workflows. EDCH serves as the host environment for multiple KERs, which have been integrated into its core services for the Diamond OA community. In parallel, collaboration with DOAJ strengthened the curation of journal data in DDH.

Within the project itself, several KERs are functionally interlinked. The OJS Diamond Plugins and OJS Core Enhancements share a joint technical base and ensure interoperability between OJS installations and discovery or monitoring services. The Guide to Scholarly Indexes and the DDH reinforce each other by connecting journal records with indexing criteria and visibility workflows, while the OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard consumes DDH data for analytics. The Guide is also exposed to users via the Discoverability Companion (DISCO) plugin (part of OJS Diamond Plugins). The Living Handbook consolidates documentation and methodological outputs from all KERs, serving as a unifying resource for guidance and training. These connections turn separate developments into an operationally coherent and exploitable framework.

4 SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK

4.1 Principles and process underlying the sustainability framework

Building on the approach outlined in D7.2, CRAFT-OA applied a framework based on a KER-driven model: each result has a responsible organisation, a named champion, and a defined pathway for continuity. During the project, exploitation was coordinated through KER champions, who acted as operational leads and short-term owners to guide development and integration. As the project moves into its sustainability phase, these roles evolve: long-term ownership and hosting are transferred to institutional partners capable of maintaining the results beyond CRAFT-OA.

To support this transition the sustainability framework also adds an additional layer of reflection structured around five key dimensions: 1) ownership, 2) hosting, 3) technical support, 4) editorial and content updates, and 5) community and user management. These dimensions provide a common frame of reference for all results and are reflected in the consolidated sustainability table (Section 4 below), which brings together all KERs across the five dimensions.

The development of this framework was an iterative process carried out throughout the project, supported by regular WP7 meetings and individual work with KER champions. These exchanges focused on refining ownership and maintenance responsibilities and aligning them with the project's governance structure. The sustainability sessions held in October 2025 provided an opportunity to validate it. Discussions, building on inputs from KER champions, addressed interdependencies between results, key strengths, remaining risks and pending issues that required further coordination before the project's end. As a result, the consolidated table serves as both a coordination tool and a reference point for transition planning beyond the project.

In addition to the operational mechanisms described above, CRAFT-OA sustainability is strongly rooted in community participation and integration within broader ecosystems that have guided development (i.e. PKP, OpenAIRE, OPERAS/EDCH, EOSC). Partners and their networks co-designed results around concrete needs and contexts, rather than top-down assumptions. This early integration of community perspectives ensured that each development was anchored in real workflows, creating a direct line between design, adoption and ownership. This collective foundation reduces dependencies and reinforces the long-term viability of results.

4.2 Diversity of results and sustainability pathways

The results developed within CRAFT-OA demonstrate a broad diversity in origin, scope, and function – from embedded software components integrated into existing infrastructures to newly created community and knowledge resources. Each required a customised approach to long-term maintenance and governance, reflecting the varied operational realities across the Diamond OA ecosystem. Rather than producing a single product or uniform platform, the project built a coherent portfolio of

complementary outputs designed to meet different technical, organisational, and community needs.

Several results are embedded within established infrastructures that already ensure long-term technical and organisational continuity. The OJS Core Feature Enhancements are integrated into the core release cycle of PKP, securing maintenance through PKP's developer community and governance framework. The OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard operates within the OpenAIRE MONITOR service and follows its release, support, and funding model, ensuring continuity through OpenAIRE's infrastructure operations.

Other results were newly created within CRAFT-OA to address emerging community needs and to strengthen knowledge exchange within the Diamond OA ecosystem. The Living Handbook is hosted and maintained by FHH/SUBHH, serving as a dynamic documentation and training resource that compiles and updates practices from institutional publishers. The Guide to Scholarly Indexes, coordinated by OpenEdition in collaboration with the EDCH Tools and Technology Task Force (TTF), provides structured information on indexing criteria and policies, with plans to potential expansion, updates, and upgrades of the guide. Both services rely on editorial oversight, community engagement and institutional hosting, complemented by technical support to ensure accessibility and version control.

The DDH illustrates a hybrid form of sustainability. Developed within CRAFT-OA and now integrated with EDCH, it connects several operational layers: ICM provides technical maintenance and hosting, the product owner role has transitioned from UGOE to DOAJ. UGOE due to its networked role in national and international Institutional Publishing and/or Service Provider (IPSP) communities continues to offer administrative and editorial support around onboarding of new sources. This distributed arrangement reflects the Hub's role as a shared service linking institutional, infrastructural, and community components within the Diamond OA landscape.

The OJS Diamond Plugins have been developed and are currently maintained by consortium members with a strong role in institutional publishing. The plugins act as bridging components within the CRAFT-OA ecosystem, connecting publishing platforms with aggregators and registries. Developed to enhance interoperability and discoverability for OJS-based journals, they are currently maintained through open repositories with community contributions, with a planned transition toward an institutional maintenance model in collaboration with PKP and OpenAIRE.

In sum, sustainability in CRAFT-OA is portfolio-based: not either-or, but a spectrum where infrastructure and community mechanisms work together to secure long-term continuity.

5 SUSTAINABILITY ARRANGEMENTS FOR INDIVIDUAL KERs

The table below summarises sustainability arrangements for all CRAFT-OA KERs across five common dimensions: ownership, hosting, technical support, editorial and content updates, community and user management. It provides a consolidated reference point before the individual sustainability overviews for each KER that follows.

As outlined earlier in Section 2.2, the project's exploitation activities were structured around KER champions, who coordinated the active development, integration and uptake of each result during CRAFT-OA's implementation. The table below now reflects the transition from this project-based exploitation phase to the long-term institutional ownership and hosting arrangements that will ensure continued maintenance and use beyond the project.

KER	1) Ownership	2) Hosting Domain (D), Hosting (H), Repository (R)	3) Technical support Tech. support (T), Future versions (F), UI, UX (U)	4) Editorial & content updates	5) Community & user management
KER1 Diamond Discovery Hub	UGOE, DOAJ	D: EDCH H: ICM R: ICM	T: ICM F: ICM U: ICM	Trusted sources	UGOE and DOAJ
KER2 OJS Core Feature Enhancements	PKP	D: N/A ⁹ H: N/A R: PKP	T: PKP F: PKP developer community U: PKP	PKP developer community	N/A
KER3 OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard	OpenAIRE	D: OpenAIRE H: OpenAIRE R: Gitea	T: OpenAIRE F: OpenAIRE U: OpenAIRE	OpenAIRE, Diamond OA community	OpenAIRE
KER4 Publisher's Living Handbook for Diamond OA	FHH/ SUBHH	D: EDCH H: FHH/ SUBHH R: Moodle	T: FHH/SUBHH F: FHH/SUBHH U: FHH/SUBHH	Diamond OA community	FHH/ SUBHH
KER5 OJS Diamond Plugins	OpenAIRE, TIB	D: GitHub H: GitHub R: GitHub	T: TIB, OpenAIRE F: Diamond OA community U: N/A	TIB, OpenAIRE based on input from Diamond OA community	N/A
KER6 Guide to Scholarly Indexes	OE	D: Zenodo, GitHub H: Zenodo, GitHub R: GitHub	T: OE F: OE, EDCH TTF U: OE, EDCH TTF	OE, EDCH	OE

Table 2.

⁹ For KER2, the N/A entries reflect that this result consists of core enhancements integrated into the PKP applications and therefore does not require a separate domain, hosting or standalone community management.

KER 1 – Diamond Discovery Hub

The sustainability model of the [Diamond Discovery Hub \(DDH\)](#) is distributed among several organisations that jointly ensure the platform’s technical continuity, editorial maintenance, and community support. This distributed model guarantees long-term resilience by combining the expertise and responsibilities of technical, editorial, and other partners.

The ICM in Warsaw, which developed the first version of the DDH, will continue to provide technical support and maintenance. Its role includes hosting the platform, curating and maintaining the code repositories on GitLab, maintaining the JMEF¹⁰ and providing technical documentation. ICM will also lead the development of the next version of the system, DDH 2.0, ensuring that the platform remains technologically up to date, accessible, and scalable.

The role of product owner, fulfilled during the first development phase by UGOE, has been transferred to the DOAJ. DOAJ will be the communications channel between ICM and the EDCH Executive Committee that is ultimately responsible for the strategic and future technical development of the DDH. As product owner, DOAJ will coordinate technical and strategic developments and ensure continuous alignment with the broader goals of the Diamond OA ecosystem. To enable a smooth transition, UGOE will provide DOAJ with full documentation and background information on past developments as well as plans and ideas for future enhancement. DOAJ will continue to maintain the non-technical documentation for users and stakeholders and ensure it remains accurate and up to date.

The data that populates the DDH primarily comes from trusted sources such as institutional publishers, IPSPs, Institutional Publishing Tool & Technology Providers (IPTPs), and National Capacity Centres (NCCs). Registration of these trusted sources takes place through the [EDCH registry](#), which functions as the first validation layer. This registry filters out partners outside of scope and potential spam entries before the data reaches the DDH. Once the registration data has been received, the UGOE team evaluates it internally and creates accounts for approved sources and their representatives. UGOE therefore holds an administrative role within the DDH website and is responsible for onboarding of trusted sources by creating and managing user accounts, communicating with data providers, and offering first-level support. UGOE takes this role because of its deep embeddedness in national and international networks of institutional publishing services. The management of DDH onboarding takes place on the OPERAS confluence, thus sustained beyond the CRAFT-OA funding period.

Coordination and support with the user community are ensured through the [EDCH Forum](#), which serves as a collaborative space for the DDH community. A dedicated closed group within the forum allows trusted source representatives and experienced

¹⁰ Dumiszewski, Ł., & Mądry, K. (2025). Journal Metadata Exchange Format - an open format to share journal metadata (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17406780>

diamond experts¹¹ to discuss issues related to journal verification against the diamond criteria. These criteria form the foundation for assessing whether a journal qualifies as a diamond journal. The UGOE team will monitor the discussions and extend the [FAQs](#) based on the outcome and issues arising during the onboarding.

In addition to the core partners, the DDH will continue its collaboration with the team at Masaryk University. Together, they will monitor and, if necessary, adjust [DISCOverability companion](#) and [JMEF OJS plugins](#), maintaining alignment between OJS-based journals and the DDH requirements and metadata model. Furthermore, the collective institutions part of the EDCH will support the DDH in translating and maintaining the localisation of the DDH.

In this way, the DDH's sustainability model is grounded in a balanced distribution of technical, editorial, and community responsibilities. ICM secures the technical and developmental continuity, DOAJ oversees strategic leadership and facilitates the future developments, UGOE carries out administrative tasks and maintains communication with data providers, EDCH anchors the registry and community infrastructure, and Masaryk University supports OJS plugins related to the DDH. Together, these organisations maintain the DDH as a trusted, evolving, and sustainable service for the Diamond OA community.

KER 2 – OJS Core Feature Enhancements

OJS core feature enhancement is a collection of new features developed for the journal publishing platform OJS. The enhanced core features include advanced support for data privacy and multilingual metadata, both important especially in the European context. Furthermore, a set of new or enhanced features aimed at elevating the standard of metadata quality of diamond journals is introduced.

The CRAFT-OA project delivers major improvements to OJS in the areas of GDPR compliance, multilingual publishing, and metadata quality. OJS 3.5, released in 2025, is the first version to include these enhancements.

OJS 3.5 introduces a new invitation-based workflow for creating users and assigning roles, replacing direct user creation and ensuring explicit consent. This strengthens GDPR compliance across OJS, OMP, and OPS. The multilingualism work restructures OJS's language architecture by decoupling interface and metadata languages and adding full support for Best Current Practices (BCP) 47 language tags. Editors can change a submission's language at any stage, edit metadata for legacy languages, see galley languages clearly, and benefit from language-specific URLs that make all language versions indexable by search engines. Together, these changes resolve limitations in multilingual publishing and improve metadata quality and discoverability. OJS 3.5 also introduces controlled vocabularies, allowing metadata terms such as keywords and disciplines to include identifiers and authoritative sources.

¹¹ Those are experienced editors, often with a strong national role, who verified the first data sets for the DDH and with whom the verification guidelines had been developed during the project.

The developed core feature enhancements¹² will become an integral part of releases of OJS and will also be available for OMP (for publishing books) and OPS (for publishing preprints). The results will be maintained and further developed by the PKP developer community after the end of the project.

KER 3 – OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard

The OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard is designed for long-term sustainability through its integration within the OpenAIRE MONITOR service and its operation on OpenAIRE's trusted European research infrastructures. This embedding ensures technical reliability, interoperability, and continuity well beyond the project's lifetime.

The service is maintained and governed by OpenAIRE, benefiting from its established operational framework, service management processes, and strategic alignment with the EOSC. Through this integration, the Publisher Dashboard becomes part of a robust ecosystem of OpenAIRE services that already support a large number of organisations across Europe. OpenAIRE will cover the major technical and infrastructural costs, including:

- Integration into the OpenAIRE Graph;
- Continuous support for data aggregation and validation;
- Support for the metadata curation;
- Metadata enrichment processes;
- Hosting, maintenance, and platform updates.

While OpenAIRE will continue to underwrite these fundamental costs, a lightweight subscription model will be introduced to sustain long-term operations and user support (e.g., hosting, maintenance, continuous improvement). To encourage early adoption and community engagement, participating pilots and all stakeholders interested in the service will benefit from a three-year subscription-free period following the end of the CRAFT-OA project. During this phase, OpenAIRE will ensure operational coverage, user feedback collection, and iterative improvements based on pilot experiences.

The sustainability of the Publisher Dashboard is being further reinforced through ongoing discussions on alignment with the EDCH. This prospective collaboration aims to enhance the service's visibility and integration within the broader Diamond OA ecosystem, while OpenAIRE and EDCH provide overarching coordination and ensure operational continuity across services beyond the project's lifetime. Together, they will contribute to a coherent and sustainable European framework for supporting institutional and community-driven Diamond OA publishing.

¹² Preparatory work on the expanded metadata model planned for OJS 3.6 was initiated within CRAFT-OA, while the full implementation will be included in the upcoming release. OJS 3.6 extends the metadata work with a new machine-readable contributor model, separate contributor types (persons, organizations, anonymous), native support for CRediT roles, and structured data citation fields. These developments improve interoperability with Crossref, DataCite, ORCID, and OpenAIRE, and strengthen OJS as a platform for high-quality, multilingual Diamond OA publishing. See D4.2 for details.

Moreover, the Publisher Dashboard will continue to evolve through the active engagement of key stakeholders and the broader Diamond OA community, ensuring that the service remains relevant, responsive to user needs, and technically up to date.

In the long term, the Publisher Dashboard will operate as a stable, community-driven service within the OpenAIRE portfolio, continuously adapted to the evolving needs of institutional publishers and policy frameworks. Its sustainability model combines technical robustness, financial viability, and stakeholder trust, ensuring that Diamond OA publishers across Europe can rely on a transparent, data-driven, and sustainable monitoring tool to support Open Science practices.

KER 4 – Publisher’s Living Handbook

The Living Handbook is a reference work that offers dynamic documentation of project results and makes them accessible in one central location. All content is and will be available fully OA. The platform’s design allows for future content expansion, with entries able to be enriched with interactive elements following the conclusion of the project.

The sustainability of the Publisher’s Living Handbook for Diamond Open Access (Living Handbook) is anchored within the Diamond OA community, ensuring long-term viability and expansion. Technical sustainability is provided by the SUBHH (Hamburg State and University Library). To maintain the technical infrastructure of the Living Handbook, it is implemented using the Learning Management System (LMS) Moodle in cooperation with the service provider lern.link (a Moodle Premium Certified Partner). Moodle is a free Open Source software package. The software is developed and supported by a large international community. The subcontractor will handle hosting through October 2027. The Living Handbook is operated on shared servers, managing its technical support and maintenance. Regular updates and related adjustments are performed, alongside daily data backups, ensuring consistent operation and data security. The technical implementation of the Living Handbook is carried out with as few adjustments as necessary and is largely standardised in order to make maintenance and security as sustainable as possible. Thus, the Living Handbook can be easily migrated to another subcontractor if necessary.

Moreover, the Living Handbook is scalable in terms of capacity and scope, enabling it to grow and adapt over time. It is publicly available as a subdomain of dianas.org and therefore a dynamic component of the EDCH.

The editorial sustainability of the Living Handbook is to be supported by an international editorial board, comprising members from European NCCs engaged in Diamond OA publishing. Discussions with NCCs are ongoing to identify individual representatives from their networks to join the editorial board, ensuring that the editorial direction and further structural development of the Handbook lie in the hands of the European Diamond OA community. The Editorial Board will be mainly responsible for conceptual development and expansion of content.

The German NCC, SeDOA, has confirmed its participation in the editorial board and its ongoing support for the Living Handbook. As part of its commitment, SeDOA will also work to build its own knowledge base based on the structure and principles of the Living Handbook. Currently, SeDOA is exploring the integration of its knowledge base into the platform, a step that would serve as a model for other NCCs, further enhancing the sustainability and adaptability of the Diamond OA ecosystem. FHH/SUBHH is both KER owner for the Living Handbook and responsible for the knowledge base in SeDOA. This offers potential for synergies for the Living Handbook.

This collaborative model enables the Living Handbook to highlight country-specific topics, fostering greater equity in the dissemination of knowledge and enhancing visibility for localised contributions to the Diamond OA movement. Initially, the core version of the Living Handbook will feature reference entries solely in English, with future provisions to support content in other European languages.

KER 5 – OJS Diamond Plugins

The long-term sustainability of the OJS Diamond plugins is a key consideration for ensuring their continued relevance and usability within the scholarly publishing ecosystem. Currently, each plugin is maintained by its original developers – Dulip Whitanage and Radek Gomola – who host the code in their respective GitHub repositories and provide ongoing support and updates. This developer-led stewardship has proven effective, enabling agile development and rapid issue resolution.

Besides this individual commitment, the plugins have now been formally adopted at an institutional level by OpenAIRE and Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB), which provides an additional layer of sustainability beyond individual developer involvement. While the daily maintenance and version updates remain with the original developers, OpenAIRE and TIB have committed to ensuring continuity: if a developer changes roles or is no longer able to maintain the plugin, the institutions will identify and assign a new qualified developer to take over responsibility.

This hybrid sustainability model combines the strengths of individual expertise with institutional guarantees of long-term continuity. It ensures that the plugins can continue to evolve, remain interoperable with future OJS versions, and serve the needs of the scholarly publishing community over the long term.

The KER5 team also started the discussions with the PKP to explore the possibility of formally adopting the plugins into the OJS ecosystem. However, before initiating this transition, it is essential to establish a clear and sustained track record of community adoption and usage. Demonstrating that the plugins are actively used and valued by the OJS community will serve as a prerequisite for negotiating institutional support. While these conversations are still in early stages and no formal agreement has been reached, the KER participants remain committed to securing a durable and scalable maintenance framework for the plugins.

CRAFT-OA Discoverability Companion

The Discoverability Companion (DISCO) plugin is designed to enhance the visibility of scholarly journals by helping editors navigate the complex landscape of indexing requirements. Building on the Knowledge base compiled in Task 5.1, DISCO consolidates and harmonises the diverse criteria used by indexing services. While many indexes share similar requirements, they often use different terminology, which can be confusing for editors. DISCO addresses this challenge by presenting a unified inventory of requirements and their descriptions, making it easier for editors to understand and act upon them.

In addition to serving as a reference tool, DISCO offers a motivational interface: it visually indicates which indexing databases a journal may qualify for based on fulfilled criteria. This feature encourages editors to improve their journal's discoverability by meeting specific standards, ultimately supporting broader dissemination and impact.

Currently, DISCO is implemented as a plugin for the OJS platform. Its development and maintenance are managed by the original authors, who have committed to supporting it for at least three years. Looking ahead, there are plans to expand DISCO into a standalone web-based tool¹³, contingent on securing financial support from future projects or institutional partners.

KER 6 – Guide to Scholarly Indexes

The Guide to Scholarly Indexes consists of the Knowledge Base (spreadsheet in Zenodo¹⁴) and the Catalogue (repository in GitHub¹⁵) containing a list of the main indexes for academic publishing. The Guide to Scholarly Indexes provides the description of indexes' characteristics, requirements, and (meta)data collection processes. The Knowledge Base and the Catalogue only differ in terms of format and usage, but contain the same information. The Knowledge Base is publicly accessible on Zenodo; the Catalogue is publicly available on OPERAS GitHub space. The Guide also includes the prototype of a searching tool, allowing to sort the indexes based on a series of criteria. While initially coded as a standalone application in PHP, the prototype also exists as an integrated feature of the GitHub repository. The prototype searching tool, which was not planned in the project, is not publicly available yet.

At this stage, the KER6 owner is the former Task Leader, i.e. OpenEdition. It is also expected that OpenEdition takes care of the potential new developments and of any communication related to the Guide. For any major expansion, update or upgrade of the Guide, the KER owner will discuss its own suggestions within the EDCH TTF. As for the content, the Guide currently contains 20 indexes described, which represent the most used and known databases for academic publications (in OA or not). It is not expected that the pace of expansion of the Guide will be very high (less than 10 per year). The current state of the Guide was reached within the project, through the

¹³ The DOAS and its self-assessment tool developed in the project DIAMAS are a good example for such a web-based tool that is agnostic vis-à-vis and independent of the technical platform for a given journal or publishing service. See <https://diamas.fecyt.es/> for more details of the DOAS and the tool.

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17103786>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-SchollIndexes-doc/tree/main>

collaboration between the Task Leader and the task's members. As part of the sustainability plan, the KER owner together with the EDCH TTF will revisit the workflow documentation to make sure that it is aligned with the requirements of adding new entries in the future. A framework has been developed, as well as extensive guidelines, in order to allow for shared completion of new entries.

The developments should remain limited and will mostly aim at facilitating the updates and expansion of the Guide. Efforts have already been made in that direction since the achievement of the last deliverable of T5.1, and now the Knowledge Base and the Catalogue are fully aligned, thus facilitating updates. An additional decisive improvement would be to transform the Guide into a dynamic database using an online form for the updates and having online dynamic outputs. However, this was not planned in the project and should receive dedicated funding to be achieved. Therefore, the development activities will remain focused on improving the current workflow. Similarly, the prototype searching tool will be developed with minimum cost as an integrated feature of existing services.

Hosting is currently ensured through external services:

- Confluence for the internal working files
- Zenodo for the public Knowledge Base
- Github for the Catalogue (eventually including a searching tool).

While these services are seen as reliable, they qualify for being moved into an improved long-term sustainability framework. Nevertheless, all the files used rely on standard formats that could be transferred to other services at a minor cost.

Communication is an important aspect of the Guide's sustainability, as the tool should be further presented and explained in order to be fully adopted by the community. In that prospect, a self-paced training has been developed in the course of the project, reflecting the currently covered 20 indexes. With a growing number of covered indexes the training will need updates to include the latest evolutions of the Guide. Regular presentations and trainings are planned for the future. In addition, in order to make the Guide more user-friendly, it is planned to transform some of the index descriptions into step-by-step detailed documentation.

6 DEPENDENCIES, RISKS AND CONTINUITY MEASURES

This section summarises the key dependencies, risks and continuity measures identified during the sustainability planning process. It builds on the discussions held at the sustainability sessions and on subsequent exchanges with KER champions and partner representatives. While the previous subsections outlined the operational setup for each result, this section focuses on the underlying conditions that support their continuity and the factors that may affect long-term stability. The continuity of CRAFT-OA results depends on a network of practical and organisational interconnections. Each result relies on a combination of technical services, institutional support, and community involvement that must remain aligned for the results to stay operational. The analysis highlights dependencies across results, potential vulnerabilities, and the measures agreed upon among partners to mitigate risks and ensure a smooth transition beyond the project's lifetime.

KER1 – Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH)

Aspect ¹⁶	Description and planned continuation	Responsible
Product ownership transition to DOAJ	The transfer of product ownership from UGOE to DOAJ has been completed according to the roadmap. A joint communication (blog post) was published to clarify the complementary roles of DDH and DOAJ within the Diamond OA ecosystem ¹⁷ .	UGOE (transition lead), DOAJ (owner)
Data validation and trusted sources	First data collection for trusted sources continues via the EDCH registry as the first validation step. UGOE administers onboarding of trusted sources by creating accounts and first-line support. Verification guidelines and FAQs are maintained and updated based on EDCH Forum discussions, monitored by UGOE.	UGOE, EDCH/OPERAS
Community engagement and visibility	Community engagement continues through EDCH Forum and activities by individual partners, which provides a collaborative space for experts to exchange feedback. DDH is integrated into OpenAIRE Graph and through OpenAIRE Graph provides information to the Publishers' dashboards. It will be featured in communication	UGOE, EDCH/OPERAS, OpenAIRE, DOAJ

¹⁶ Dependencies, risks and/or continuity measures

¹⁷ <https://blog.doaj.org/2025/10/23/doaj-and-the-diamond-discovery-hub-working-with-the-community-to-support-open-access/>

	activities coordinated via the EDCH.	
Technical maintenance and development	ICM continues to host and maintain DDH, leading the next development cycle. Regular coordination meetings with UGOE and DOAJ ensure alignment between technical updates, community needs and product roadmap.	ICM, UGOE, DOAJ
Institutional anchoring	The long-term sustainability of DDH is based on institutional commitments by DOAJ, ICM, EDCH and UGOE rather than project-based funding. Future collaborations will build on this foundation.	UGOE (transition lead), DOAJ, ICM, EDCH/OPERAS

KER2 – OJS Core Feature Enhancements

Aspect	Description and planned continuation	Responsible
Integration within PKP core	Enhancements on multilingual metadata, GDPR-compliant user management and metadata quality have been integrated into the PKP core and included in OJS 3.5 and 3.6. Their maintenance continues through PKP's regular release and governance cycles, ensuring technical continuity beyond the project.	PKP
Collective sustainability model	Long-term sustainability is ensured through PKP's established community governance. European partners (TSV and TIB) remain part of the developer and user community, providing feedback and alignment with Diamond OA needs within future PKP developments.	PKP, TSV & TIB (liaison and feedback)

KER3 – OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard

Aspect	Description and planned continuation	Responsible
Integration within OpenAIRE MONITOR	The Publisher Dashboard is fully embedded in the OpenAIRE MONITOR service and powered by the OpenAIRE Graph. Developed and piloted with SRCE, it operates as part of OpenAIRE's existing infrastructure, benefiting from its hosting, updates and technical maintenance within	OpenAIRE

	the regular service portfolio.	
Data dependencies and interoperability	The Dashboard depends on continuous data synchronisation with the OpenAIRE Graph and relies on aggregated metadata information from the DDH, DOAJ and the individual Publishers' platforms/data sources for validated journal information. Established connections between these data sources ensure indicator accuracy and interoperability within the broader Diamond OA ecosystem.	OpenAIRE, DOAJ, UGOE
Long-term sustainability and governance	Sustainability is ensured through OpenAIRE AMKE's institutional governance and funding model. As part of OpenAIRE's core infrastructure, the service follows regular operational and policy cycles, with continued feedback and coordination through OpenAIRE's community mechanisms connecting to Diamond OA stakeholders.	OpenAIRE

KER4 – Publisher's Living Handbook for Diamond OA (Living Handbook)

Aspect	Description and planned continuation	Responsible
Integration within EDCH and technical setup	The Living Handbook is implemented on Moodle and integrated as a subdomain within EDCH. This setup supports technical continuity and availability by pooling the Living Handbook with other EDCH components such as the DDH and Registry. Hosting, maintenance and updates are the responsibility of FHH/SUBHH.	FHH/SUBHH, EDCH
Editorial sustainability and community model	FHH/SUBHH coordinates editorial activities, supported by EDCH NCCs, contributing to content updates and localisation. A toolkit for editors and editorial guidelines ensures consistent quality and supports continuity of updates after the project.	FHH/SUBHH, EDCH
Future alignment and reuse	The Living Handbook concept is being further developed through reuse within the SeDOA project (German national node),	FHH/SUBHH, EDCH

	linking the handbook to national developments, thus strengthening collaboration within the European Diamond OA communities.	
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KER5 – OJS Diamond Plugins

Aspect	Description and planned continuation	Responsible
Integration and access	The OJS Diamond Plugins are released through the PKP plugin gallery and remain available on GitHub. Integration into PKP's infrastructure ensures long-term accessibility and visibility within the global OJS ecosystem.	PKP, MU
Maintenance and updates	Maintenance and updates are carried out by plugin authors (Radek Gomola, Dulip Withanage and by contributors from the PKP developer community. Besides this individual commitment, the plugins have now been formally adopted at an institutional level by OpenAIRE and TIB, which provides an additional layer of sustainability beyond individual developer involvement. Future compatibility with new OJS versions follows PKP's established release cycle.	PKP, MU, AMU, OpenAIRE, TIB

KER6 – Guide to Scholarly Indexes

Aspect	Description and planned continuation	Responsible
Integration and access	The Guide to Scholarly Indexes is coordinated by OpenEdition and made openly available through the Knowledge Base (Zenodo) and the Catalogue (GitHub). The Guide is referenced in the DISCO plugin and the Living Handbook, ensuring its continued use across Diamond OA tools and documentation.	OpenEdition, EDCH TTF, MU
Updates	Updates follow an established workflow, with community feedback collected via the EDCH Forum. Future development of the Guide will depend on additional support,	OpenEdition, EDCH TTF

	allowing a transition to a dynamic database with automated updates and easier maintenance.	
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Table 3.

7 CONCLUSIONS

CRAFT-OA has reached the point where sustainability is a set of concrete operational arrangements. Each result is positioned within an existing organisational and technical framework that can maintain it beyond the project's lifetime.

The approach taken in CRAFT-OA reframes sustainability from ownership of individual outcomes to stewardship across a network. Technical components, documentation resources and community processes are now connected through established infrastructures such as PKP and OpenAIRE, and supported by institutional partners who have taken over defined operational and governance roles. These are further aligned with the emerging EDCH, ensuring continuity through both infrastructure-level and institutional commitments. This distributed model replaces the idea of a single successor platform with a federated set of interoperable services maintained collectively across organisations.

The project's contribution is therefore structural: it has equipped the Diamond OA publishing landscape with standards, interfaces and governance pathways that enable long-term operation while reducing reliance on project-based funding cycles. The results demonstrate how public infrastructures can share responsibility for maintenance, further development and user support within a collective service environment.

With these mechanisms in place, CRAFT-OA concludes as a completed phase in the evolution of Diamond OA, one that translates coordination into durable capacity and provides a credible foundation for continued collaboration among infrastructures, service providers and scholarly communities.

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